

Help sheet: Usage

explanatory notes:

the following explanations can help you find the right option, if you are unsure.

I spend ... per day on social media.

Most smartphone allow you to check how long you have been using each app.

I prefer visiting ... social media sites.

If your favorite social media site is not listed or you cannot decide, please select option C (3 blocks).

I post ... on social media.

Messenger apps are also considered social media. Social media sites include:

I watch ... videos per day in real time (streaming).

Streaming involves playing audio and video content in real time, meaning that it does not need to be downloaded previously [1].

I watch videos in real time (streaming) in ... quality.

Depending on the streaming provider, the default setting is usually Full HD or 4K.

I play ... video games on my smartphone every day.

Most smartphones allow you to check how long you have been using each app.

I send and receive ... text messages and emails per day.

This includes not only emails and text messages, but also messenger apps (Whats App, Signal, Telegram, ...), direct messages via social networks (Instagram, Facebook, Snapchat, ...) and chat messages (Twitch, ...).

I use generative AI or digital assistants (Siri, ...) ... times a day.

Generative AI includes chat-bots (ChatGPT, Gemini, Copilot, ...), image generation (Midjourney, DALL-E, Stable Diffusion, ...), and video generation (Sora, ...).